

Assessment on population density of Lar gibbon (*Hylobates lar*) at Ywar Kaing Kaung Village in Dawna Mountain Range Corridor, Hpa-an District, Kayin State, Myanmar

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Abstract

The population of White handed gibbons are decreasing with threatening from human disturbance and lack of any information about the taxonomic status and ecology of Lar gibbon in Myanmar. So, the study area will be selected to Ywar Kaing Kaung Village, Dawna Mountain Range Corridor, Kayin State, Myanmar. The study period will be conducted from June 2017 to March 2018. The study will be concentrated on demographic as well as socio-ecological factors, social organization and identify site-specific conservation measures. The research finding will help in quantifying the current status and demography of scattered population of Lar gibbon in different forest habitats as the type of study area. Totally 25 individuals were recorded. The eco-behavioral study will help to understand whether these populations can withstand the substantial change of their habitat. Moreover, identifying the food resources and habitat preferences of Lar gibbon will also help in future prospects of in-situ and ex-situ conservation of primate habitat with the help of local conservation group and forest department.

Keywords: population, conservation

Introduction

Tropical forest are the most ancient, more diverse, and the most ecologically complex of land communities, occupying only 7% of the earth's land surface, tropical forests probably sustain over half of the life form (Wilson 1988, Myers 1992). However, approximately 5.8 million hectares of the remaining tropical forests were cleared, burned, logged and converted to agricultural and human settlements without historical precedent annually (Achard *et al.* 2002).

About 90% of primates live in and the best flagship species for tropical forests, however, over 40% of the total 634 primate species are threatened to extinction due to combination of habitat degradation and anthropogenic activities (PCI 2013). The fact that gibbons are one of the most threatened Families of primate and its numbers have been in dramatic decline over the past 30–40 years (Bodmer *et al.* 1991). As one of the endangered primates, Lar gibbon (*Hylobates lar*) are being threatened and their population is also continuously declining (Sutherland, 2002).

The inter-birth interval is particularly long in gibbon species (2 - 3 years) and spacing of gibbon groups are territoriality and monogamy. The existence of exclusive territories imposes restrictions on population density (Mitani, 1990). However, very limited data are available for gibbon in terms of their population and demographic trends

The present study was carried out with the following objectives:

- to evaluate the present status and demography of Lar gibbon populations
- to explore the utilization of foraging range by Lar gibbon
- to classify the land cover changes in study area

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Materials and Methods

Study area

Ywar Kaing Kaung village is located at 16° 56'14" N and 97° 56' 12" E and 2 km² area in Pai Kyu sub-township, Hlaing Bwe Township, Hpa An District, Karen State. The relief of Karen State is mountainous with the Dawna Range Corridor.

Study Period

Data collection took place 1st to 6th January and 9th to 14th February for 5 consecutive days initially for population density estimation.

Fig 1. The study area of Ywar Kaing Kaung village

Methods

Estimation of gibbon density conducted line transect sampling, fixed-point counts and triangulation and direct count methods (Brockelman and Ali, 1987). Analysis techniques most suitable to estimate densities of gibbon populations are variants of the fixed point method, during which the loud morning songs of the gibbons are monitored from fixed listening points (Brockelman and Ali, 1987). Three listening points were selected from with distance 500m between them and recorded only duet calling bouts which gibbon calls were monitored during five consecutive day between 05:00h am to 10:00h am each morning and 13:00h pm to 18:00h pm each evening in the study area.

The calculated density estimates using the following formula and correction factors:

$$D = n / [p(m) \times E]$$

n = the number of groups heard in an area, $p(m)$ = the estimated proportion of groups expected to sing during a sample period of m days, E = the effective listening area. The correction factor $p(m)$ was determined at each site with the formula: $p(m) = 1 - [1 - p(1)]^m$, $p(1)$ = the singing probability for any given day, m = the number of survey days (Brockelman and Ali, 1987).

Analysis of group territories (foraging range)

The territories range size was determined by the location of song-bouts, location of feeding sites, travel routes, and intergroup encounters, and the analysis of photos to determine habitat boundaries. Analysis using minimum convex polygons (animal movement analysis) in Home Range Analysis and land cover examine by (ArcMap 10.1).

Result

The results of total population estimate based on the aural evidence and the direct sightings, there were 25 individuals belongs to eight habituated groups of lar gibbon reliably heard from all listening posts radius of 1 km. Direct sightings were recorded within the 0.6 km radius in LP1, LP2 and LP3 and Naung Bo village four separate gibbon groups were directly sighted in LP1, four groups directly sighted in LP2 and three groups directly sighted in LP3 and LP4 in one group respectively (Table 2).

The number of call phrases in each song, their sequences, and duration are a slight difference in calling activity among the lar gibbons, who called equally frequently between 5:00 am and 6:00 am the sequences of great song calls phrases 12 minutes in group 2 and 10 minute in two song call phrases in group 5 and 6 respectively .The resulting population density estimates/km² for gibbon groups were on average 2.23 or 6.69 individual per km².

Plate 1. The activity of lar gibbon groups in different habitat types in Ywar Kaing Kaung Village

Table 1. Population structure of Lar gibbon species in Ywar Kaing Kaung Village

No.	Group	Adult		Juvenile	Infant	Group Size
		Male	Female			
1	Group1	1	1	1		3
2	Group2	1	3		1	5
3	Group3	1	1	1		3
4	Group4	1	2			3
5	Group5	1	1			2
6	Group6	1	1			2
7	Group7	1	2			3
8	Group8	1	1	1	1	4
Total Population		8	12	3	2	25

Table 2. The population structure and status of lar gibbon species in study area

Listening Post	Group	Individuals	Sex			Ages			Colour	
			Male	Female	Unknown	Adult	Juvenile	Infant	Black	White
LP1	1	3	1	1	1	2	1			3
	3	3	1	1	1	2	1	1		2
	4	3	1	2		3				3
	5	2	1	1		2			2	
LP2	1	3	1	1		2	1			3
	3	3	1	1		2	1	1		2
	4	3	1	2		3				3
	8	4	1	1	1	2	1	1		4
LP3	2	5	1	3	1	4		1	1	4
	3	3	1	1		2	1		1	2
	7	3	1	2		3			1	2
LP4	6	2	1	1		2				2

Fig 2. The comparison of foraging range and song duration activity of lar gibbon species in Ywar Kaing Kaung Village

Fig 3. The foraging range of Lar gibbon group 1, 2, 3 and 4

Fig 4. The foraging range of Lar gibbon group 5, 6, 7 and 8

Fig 5. The analysis of Landcover changes in study area (2009-2017)

Discussion

The gibbons were not scary on human activities and they were very closing with the villagers, like habituated gibbons. The estimation of gibbon density group was height density was 2.23 groups or 6.69 individual per km² within the area of 2 km². However, spatial distribution of the lar gibbon groups within the main area is very cramped for space. On the block of this area will lead to compete for the same niche, where competition for the same resources are higher so that this pressure becomes lower and populations or species change less rapidly in future decades. The classification of the forest structure components are important indicators of habitat suitability for lar gibbon (Chapman *et al.* 2004). It assumed that the village and human population are being developed and the households of village were almost reduplicated within about two decade. Consequently it caused the gibbon habitats have been degraded and territory was also restricted with the forest patches. Action must be taken now to safeguard this area, threats to the habitat have one inevitable outcome: these populations will be seriously threatened in the future unless action is taken.

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